

IMPORTANCE INTERNET IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of the Internet in modern education. The author discusses the benefits of the Internet and its benefits for students.

The Internet, the most useful modern-day technology that helps us not only in our daily lives but also in our professional lives. It is widely used for educational purposes for gathering information and doing research or adding to the knowledge of various subjects. The Internet plays an extremely important role in education. There's no doubt that everybody prefers Google in this modern era for their queries, problems or doubts. Popular search engines such as Yahoo, Google, etc. are people's top option because they offer easy and fast access in just a few seconds to the vast amount of information. It includes a wealth of knowledge which can be searched at any time. The internet has improved technology, communication and online entertainment.

Today it has become more important in the world as well as a powerful tool favored by all. Everyone needs internet for some purpose or other. Students need to search the internet for

information about exams, curriculum, results, etc. To achieve success in student life you can also follow these steps for students. Importance of the internet in education to the students means making it easier for them to research things, and to relearn the content taught in the school. It's used by people according to their needs and interests.[1;85]

In many ways it is difficult to discuss any aspect of contemporary society without taking the Internet into consideration. Many people's lives are so thoroughly saturated with digital technology that the once-obvious distinction between being online or offline now does not do justice to a situation where the Internet is always implicitly on. Nevertheless, it is often found that younger generations are unable to communicate as a distinct body of the Internet. Alternatively, electronic activities have been part of the lives of young people since birth, and are considered to be a

fundamental requirement of modern life, much like air, water or electricity. So speaking of the Internet and education in many ways simply means talking about contemporary education. The Internet is already an integral element of education in (over)developed nations, and we can be sure that its educational significance across the globe will continue to increase over this decade.

The use of internet for education helps to streamline the sharing of information and communication. It lets students access lectures online and refer to relevant study material in various multimedia formats. It also helps teachers by letting them use various tools in their curriculum. Access to internet also allows retired teachers or volunteers to offer educational services to children in poor communities or even in different countries. The importance of internet in education is made evident through the following points:[2;46]

Higher interactivity. The internet has provided a large boost to interactivity in student-teacher interactions. With the inclusion of social media apps and online learning platforms that provide real-time assistance, teachers and students are now able to engage in dynamic interactions whenever the need arises.

Flexibility of learning. Resource and location constraints of conventional modes of education do not apply to online learning and its platforms. Access to the Internet allows one to learn their study material online remotely and at their own pace. It also serves as a 24x7 support system for students and teachers to interact. It also allows working professionals to enroll in courses that fit their schedules.

Cost-effectiveness. Purchasing books and study material is usually an expensive affair. However, with online courses and other sources of information, accessing study material online has become cost-efficient.

Dynamic and actively updated. A large number of online websites and data archives are able to receive real-time updates. This allows users to download information that is up to date, verified and ready for distribution.

Multimedia-integration. Studies have shown that we usually consume data faster and more efficiently through audio-visual format. These formats include multimedia, infographics, slideshows etc. These multimedia formats can be actively used in courses and lessons thanks to the use of the internet.

Now that we've had a look at the importance of internet in education. Let us now examine how the use of the internet in education in recent years has benefited students.

Benefits of internet for students:[3]

Improvements in communication. Communication between teachers and students used to be linear. However, the internet has added a new level of interactivity to this relationship. Using the internet allows for interactive communication between the two parties irrespective of time and distance constraints. The process is made more seamless through various social apps or digital platforms.

Higher acceptance of online certification. Online learning and certifications were not considered competitive or reliable up until a few years ago. Associated universities and colleges with online programs usually lacked adequate accreditation. However,

that scenario has undergone a shift, with many universities now offering distance learning programs and subsequent online certification courses.

More students opting for online education. A testament to the success of the internet's improvement of the educational field lies in the fact that more are opting for online mediums of learning than ever before.

The internet has provided an impetus to the growing education sector. This new

dimension of accessibility and interactivity has enhanced the quality of educational resources and the quantity of relevant data that can be seamlessly transferred even from one point to another. This momentum can be expected to rise as more internet-enabled devices and data accessibility becomes commonplace in rural locations and to all socio-economic communities.

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